

THE ROLE OF FAIRY TALES IN TEACHING ENGLISH AT PRIMARY SCHOOL LEVEL

Maftuna Jumabayeva

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute
Undergraduate student

Abstract: The main aims of this article is to show benefits of fairy tales for the development of young children. One of the productive methods that actively acquaint pupils with knowledge is studying fairy tales at English lessons. It can improve their imagination, also helps connect the elements of literary and linguistic analysis.

Key words: fairy tale, school age, methods of teaching English, fantasy, Cinderella, Peter and the Wolf.

INTRODUCTION

At the initial stage of education, it is very important to interest children in learning, so the English teacher has a very important task not only to teach language but also to develop an interest in its study. However the question arises: how to do it. Therefore, a lot teachers in the classroom trying to use interesting tasks a lot of visibility and so on. Nevertheless, unfortunately with most of these tasks the children only get bored, tired of the large number of variety in class.

It is known that teaching English to elementary school children is very difficult. They get exhausted very quickly and get distracted. The academic style is not suitable here. It is a bit challenging to attract the attention of children with text task, it is much better to conduct lessons in a playful and unobtrusive form.

In modern pedagogical practice, the communicative method of learning English is given special attention. It is believed that this is the most effective method of learning the language, allowing students to entertainingly and unobtrusively to master the intricacies of the English language. Today it is believed that during the study of English, students should master not only all language skills, but also have a clear idea of the traditions, culture, history, and realities of life of residents of English-speaking countries. English fairy tales are quite suitable for this purpose. I will say, even more, the use of English fairy tales in the classroom improves individual learning, promotes the development of motivation. It is necessary to strive to ensure that students receive satisfaction not only from the plot of the tale but also from the realization of what they understand in English, which is described in it. Moreover, the use of fairy tales in the classroom contributes to the individualization of learning and the development of motivation of speech activity of students.

So, a fairy tale is an inexhaustible source of games, fantasies, learning new

things. It is a strong motivating factor that satisfies the need of students in the novelty of the material studied and the variety of exercises performed, which activates the students' mental activity, makes the learning process no more attractive and interesting, makes you worry and worried, which forms a powerful incentive to learn the language. Using fairy tales in the lessons, we introduce children to the characters, traditions, and find common with Russian fairy tales. It is important to use authentic material in this process. With the help of a fairy tale, a teacher can develop almost all the skills and abilities, teach to predict, talk about the contents of a fairy tale. In children of primary school age, there is a change in the leading activity from play (in preschool age) to educational, which helps them move to the next stage of development associated with the activation of mental activity and with a new social status, new relationships with others.

Thus, I believe that the use of fairy tales when teaching introductory reading in English lessons allows you to add variety to the content of the lesson, broadens the general horizons and communicative culture of younger students, develops a language guess, a sense of language, increases the interest of students in the language, and therefore and motivation for learning. Without a doubt, using a fairy tale will improve the process of learning English. A fairy tale, like any other element of the communicative method of language learning, diversifies classes, allows students to learn the necessary information easily and entertainingly, to develop language skills. But it should be understood that the effectiveness of using fairy tales in learning English depends on the rational organization of classes.

“*Once upon a time, there was...*”. These are the magic words that start many a fairy tale and transport us back in time to our childhoods and the fantastical world of our imaginations. A place where princesses and princes can defeat all the obstacles that cross their paths, including big, scary and dangerous dragons. Do you remember how happy and excited you felt when someone you loved took the time to read you a fairy tale? Chances are that you probably haven't read that fairy tale in a while, yet, you would easily be able to retell it in a wink of an eye. This is undeniable proof that fairy tales are memorable and that they continue to live in our minds long after we hear or read the classic phrase: “And they all lived happily ever after.”

Albert Einstein defended that: “*If you want your children to be intelligent, read them fairy tales. If you want them to be more intelligent, read them more fairy tales.*” Judging by his track record, this is the type of advice that cannot be taken lightly! Most children will have come into contact with fairy tales in their native language, so these stories can provide them with a safe and familiar context to learn a foreign language in, too. So, when they learn a fairy tale in English, understanding the text becomes less of a problem as they already know the content. Another of the many benefits of fairy tales is that they develop children's emotional well-being by

teaching them morals in a context that they can understand and easily identify with. They can show them the importance of being kind, supporting friends through hardships as well as the fundamental need to be resilient.

METHODS

Fairy tale activity ideas

Post-reading activities are a great way to continue to engage children after the story and can be used to develop children’s emotional intelligence, creativity and critical thinking skills. According to Psychologist Daniel Goleman, who specialises in emotional intelligence, emotional intelligence (EI) is the ability to identify, assess and control one’s emotions as well as to understand and manage the emotions of others. Goleman defends that EI or emotional competencies are not innate talents but rather a learned capacity that must consciously be worked on and developed. This being the case we must develop the following sub-skills with our children: self-awareness, self-regulation, social skills, empathy and motivation.

Post-reading activities for Cinderella

Discussion topics/questions:

How does Cinderella’s step-family treat her? Does she treat them in the same way? Why?

How does Cinderella overcome her problems?

Why do the animals help Cinderella?

What can the fairy godmother do that Cinderella can’t do?

Post-reading activities for Peter and the Wolf

Discussion questions/topics:

Why do the bird and duck get angry with each other? How else could they react?

Why is Peter’s grandfather angry with him?

What does Peter teach his grandfather?

Why does the bird do what Peter tells him to do?

What can Peter do that the wolf can’t do?

What is the moral of this story?

Writing:

Write your own fairy tale using the Pixar Structure:

Once upon a time, there was...

Every day, ...

One day, ...

Because of that, ...

Until finally...

Snow White
Draw a line from each picture to the correct word

Snow White
Prince
Dwarf
Huntsmen
Magic Mirror
King
Queen

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It should be noted that the children do not possess enough language to discuss these questions in English. Because of this, it is important to adopt a time-out strategy where you speak L1 during the discussion. Slowly introduce one or two new English words that reflect the main points of your discussion and get the children to repeat these words. After the discussion ends, go back to these words and discuss them with the children by asking questions like: How do you say concept in discussion in English? What is the English word for concept in discussion? You can help children structure this new vocabulary by creating a classroom wall dictionary where the children write and illustrate the new words that they are learning. They then have easy access and are constantly reminded of the words they are picking up naturally during storytelling.

RESULTS

According to several critics, there are a number of reasons why teachers use Children’s stories:

- Stories are motivating and fun creating a desire to communicate. They develop positive attitudes and help children to keep on learning. Positive affective factor facilitate acquiring a second language. Children will learn better if they have a

positive attitude towards what they are doing.

– Stories exercise the imagination. Children imagine sceneries, characters and so on about a story. For example, if they become personally involved in a story they can identify with some characters.

– Stories provide a rich resource for education about human societies, offering Insights into life in many different communities and into complex cultures.

– Stories are a useful tool in linking fantasy and imagination with the child’s real world. So children can make sense of their everyday life. Stories help children to understand the world and to share it with others. “Nine to twelve -year-olds Are developing their ability to appreciate other viewpoints. At this age stories about family and friends should not only reassure children about themselves but also provide them with new insights into how other families and children cope with various situations. Children at this age enjoy stories that extend their experiences (Brumfit, Moon and Tongue 1991: 185). On the other hand, there is a need to make language learning easier for young children by relating it to their experience in everyday life.

ANALYSIS

SELECTION OF STORYBOOKS

Stories must be chosen depending on the age and the linguistic level of the pupils. Moreover, there must be a particular purpose when selecting a story so that it will carry the ideas the teacher wishes to focus on. Another important question to think about is whether to use simplified or authentic storybooks for the children. There are many authentic storybooks written for English-speaking children, which are also suitable for those learning English. Moreover, authentic storybooks are full of examples of real Language although simplified stories can be easier for the Primary Education pupils (Ellis and Brewster 1991: 9). Children sometimes already know the story the teacher is going to tell. Genesee argues that choosing stories, which are culturally familiar, may be especially helpful because prior knowledge of characters and plots may make the stories potentially more comprehensible to the learners than unfamiliar ones. If a child already knows the story in his first language he will be able to follow the English version of the same story. S/He already knows the plot and the teacher can facilitate his/her understanding by using body language or using pictures. Stories can be chosen to support a cross-curricular teaching approach. They can develop ideas in a variety of different subject areas. They can explain concepts by providing illustrations of practical applications. The teacher has to grade the input the children receive by means of stories from Less complicated to more complicated ones. If the story is very difficult to understand the teacher can modify or simplify it. Ellis and Brewster (1991: 18-19) give some possible Solutions. The teacher must check the clarity of the text and the vocabulary. Consequently, it

may be necessary to substitute familiar words or expressions for more unfamiliar ones. That is usually the case with idioms. They are difficult to understand for children so the teacher will change them for easier words. It is also interesting to check the word order, as it can be difficult to understand.

CONCLUSION

Using story telling is a motivating activity. The teacher of English fulfils most of the objectives for the English subject in Primary Education given by the Ministry. However, there are more reasons to use them in class. Stories exercise imagination and it is also a way of helping pupils to learn in all areas of their curriculum. However, it is not an easy activity. The teacher has to develop a number of skills to improve his/her storytelling. In Addition, the children have to develop their concentrating and listening skills by means of the illustrations or while listening stage tasks. The teacher has to plan a number of story-based activities for his/her class. Children develop the four skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing, but with an emphasis on oral skills. Children do the activities autonomously so that cooperation among pupils is promoted and, consequently, the pupil-to-pupil interaction as well. They become autonomous in their own learning processes And children learn to learn for themselves.

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